

Title: Tractography protocols for the neonatal brain, standardised against the adult human and macaque

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Synopsis (100 words):

The neonatal brain undergoes rapid development in the months after birth. Diffusion tractography is a unique method for probing developing white matter connections. We present a novel and comprehensive library of tractography protocols for the neonatal brain, whilst ensuring correspondence with previously developed protocols for the adult and macaque brain. We demonstrate protocol robustness across data quality and show that the resultant tracts capture a-priori known trends in white matter microstructure. We show that these protocols open avenues for quantitative comparisons across the lifespan, but also species, which we exemplify by revealing developmental trends in connectivity patterns.

Summary of main findings (250 characters, ~35 words):

We develop a novel library of diffusion tractography protocols for the neonatal brain, consistent with those for the adult and macaque brain; we demonstrate robustness against variation in data quality and potential for lifespan/cross-species comparisons.

Introduction:

The neonatal brain undergoes rapid growth and maturation in the initial months of life¹⁻³ and its developmental trajectory has functional implications, for instance for the occurrence of neurodevelopmental disorders⁴. Diffusion tractography is a unique tool for mapping white matter (WM) tracts in-vivo and may be used to explore the micro- and macro-structural development of tracts. Here, we develop a novel library of 42 tractography protocols for the neonatal brain, defined analogously to those previously developed for the adult human and macaque brain⁵. We demonstrate protocol robustness against data quality and show that they capture a-priori known developmental trends of WM microstructure. Furthermore, we quantitatively compare neonatal, adult and macaque connectivity patterns and reveal unique potential for mapping connectivity differences and similarities across the lifespan and primate species.

Methods:

Protocols were developed for 42 (19 bilateral and 4 commissural) WM tracts, in correspondence with the ones developed for the adult and macaque brain, in XTRACT⁵. The protocols used standard-space seed, waypoint, exclusion and termination masks and were defined analogously across diverse brains, although different in geometry and exact location. The MNI-space adult protocols were used as starting points. A non-linear warp field was used to roughly align the adult protocol masks to a 40 week post-menstrual age (PMA) neonatal template⁶, which were then manually refined to ensure robust tracking for the neonate (Fig1a).

We used high-quality dMRI data from 445 neonates scanned at 29-45 weeks PMA using a bespoke setup, publicly released from the developing Human Connectome Project (dHCP)⁷ (Fig1c). Fibre orientations were modelled (up to 3 per voxel)⁸ and used for probabilistic tractography^{5,9} for each subject. Tract atlases were generated by averaging results across the group (Fig1b).

To assess robustness against data quality, we used an additional dataset of 22 neonates scanned at 37-42 weeks PMA¹⁰ (“good-quality” Oxford dataset), acquired using non-specialised hardware. Further, we generate a “standard-quality” DTI dataset (removing the $b=2000\text{s/mm}^2$ shell from the good-quality dataset) (Fig1c). Tract-atlases were compared, and inter-subject variation assessed within and between cohorts through paired correlations of thresholded normalised tract probability maps at the subject-level.

We explored whether the reconstructed tracts could capture previously reported developmental trends in WM microstructure^{3,11-17}. Taking the tract atlases as regions of interest, we calculated tract-wise fractional anisotropy (FA) and mean diffusivity (MD) for each dHCP subject (using the $b=1000\text{s/mm}^2$ shell) and used linear regression models to assess relationships between microstructure and PMA (accounting for a set of confounds) (Fig1d).

Figure 1. a) Tractography protocols are defined as sets of ROIs and rules, following XTRACT principles. b) Pre-processing for dHCP subjects: crossing-fibre modelling, tractography, and tract-atlas generation. c) Acquisition details for the three datasets used in robustness against data-quality analysis. d) Tract microstructure analysis: tract atlases were warped to the subject's native space and used as ROIs to calculate tract-wise average FA and MD for each dHCP subject. These were then used to build linear models to estimate the microstructure maturation with age.

Finally, using the correspondence of tracts across diverse brains, we directly compared connectivity within and across species. We constructed group-averaged connectivity blueprints¹⁸ (i.e. patterns of connections of different cortical areas to WM) using WM tracts as landmarks (Fig2a) and compared such patterns via Kullback-Leibler divergence^{5,18,19} (KLD) between neonatal, adult^{20,21} and macaque^{5,22} brains (Fig2b-c). Furthermore, we built blueprints for neonatal age-groups and explored changes in “predictability” (minimum row-wise KLD across brains) with age relative to the adult.

Figure 2. a) Connectivity blueprints (cortical vertices by tracts) built as the dot product of a whole-brain connectivity matrix (whole-brain WM voxels by cortical vertices) and vectorised XTRACT tracts (WM voxels by tracts). Rows are cortical connectivity patterns of a given cortical vertex; columns are cortical territories of tracts. b) Data used for cross-species and lifespan comparisons. c) Blueprints are compared using KLD, a measure of statistical similarity (step 1.), and dissimilarity maps generated by finding the minimum row-wise KLD (step 2.) across parcels.

Results:

Standardised protocols were developed for 42 major WM tracts and used to generate neonatal tract atlases (Fig3a). Crucially, these protocols provide consistently defined tracts with existing protocols for the adult and macaque⁵ (Fig3b).

Figure 3. a) Views of the population-percentage tract atlases from the 445 dHCP subjects. The tract atlases are created by averaging binarised (at a threshold of 0.1%) waytotal-normalised tract density maps across subjects. b) Cross age-group and species comparison of results from the adult human and macaque brain (XTRACT tract atlases⁵). For ease of visualisation, all tracts are viewed as maximal intensity projections with a display range of 30-100% of population coverage.

We found strong similarity between tract atlases across the three datasets (Fig4a), showing good tract delineations even with standard protocols. The average spatial correlation across all tracts was 0.89 (std=0.04) between the dHCP and Oxford, and 0.86 (std=0.08) between the dHCP and DTI data. Inter-subject variability in the tractography results was assessed within and across the subject groups relative to the dHCP dataset. Inter-subject variability was relatively consistent across datasets with, as expected, greater similarity within groups, albeit with greater variance in the DTI dataset (Fig4a). These analyses demonstrate that the protocols give reproducible tracts across varying quality datasets.

We also assessed within-tract microstructural changes using DTI measures. All tracts showed a significant increase in FA and reduction in MD with age, after confound correction. Linear regression coefficients (rate of change with age for FA/MD, Fig4b), reflect the asynchronous maturation of different tracts. In general, projection fibres mature more quickly over this period, followed by commissural and association fibres, with limbic fibres showing the slowest rates. This generally agrees with a-priori known trends from the literature^{3,11-17}.

Figure 4. a) Left: Tract atlases from an age and sex matched groups of 22 subjects from the dHCP (top) and DTI (bottom) datasets. Right: Inter-subject comparisons of tracts across datasets: each represents 231 correlations between pairs of subjects, averaged across all tracts, within and across datasets (μ =mean, σ =standard deviation). b) Tract-specific changes (colour coded by tract type – top row) in microstructure (left – FA, right – MD) with age (range = 29.3 - 45.1 weeks PMA at scan) for the dHCP subjects: y-axes correspond to the beta coefficients from the linear models.

The protocols were further used to probe connectivity differences across diverse brains, using corresponding WM tracts as landmarks. Connectivity blueprints were constructed for the neonatal, adult and macaque brains (Fig5a). Connectivity dissimilarity maps using these tracts reveal greater similarity within than across species, as expected (Fig5b: left). Comparing blueprints constructed from neonatal age-groups, we observe a trend towards greater predictability with age relative to the adult, particularly in the frontal and parietal regions (Fig5b).

Figure 5. a) Cortical territories of example WM tracts (columns of the connectivity blueprint) for the neonate, adult and macaque. b) Left: Dissimilarity maps (minimum KLD) for neonate-adult (top), neonate-macaque (middle) and adult-macaque (bottom) comparisons. Right: Change in dissimilarity between corresponding parcels with neonatal age (70 neonates per group scanned at 36-39, 39-42, and 42-45 weeks PMA) relative to the adult brain for the whole-brain (top: mean and standard deviation across all parcels) and for example parcels (bottom).

Discussion/Conclusion:

We have developed a novel library of standardised tractography protocols for the neonatal brain, consistent with those for the adult human and macaque brain, which are robust against data quality and capture accurate anatomical information. Furthermore, we explored divergence in connectivity patterns between age-groups and across species, using the tracts to construct connectivity blueprints revealing a trend of greater predictability with neonatal age relative to the adult. These protocols facilitate quantitative comparisons across the ontogenetic and phylogenetic dimensions of brain connectivity.

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